

Title: Computational Model to control Robotic arm inspired by the motor control of the Brain

Name: Gautam Ramachandra

Affiliation: upamanyuAI, Indian Institute of Science

INTRODUCTION:

Building computational models using neural networks and machine learning methods helps to understand the neural control of movement in humans which is very much helpful in building better robots and neuroprosthetics.

AIM:

To build better robots and neuroprosthetics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Here we are using simulation software's like Opensim and Mujoco for arm models. And later we came up with a biologically plausible model and integrate this model to the arm model, understanding this will essentially help in bringing out better neuro-prosthetics and robotic devices.

RESULTS:

The results are that the neural network is able to move the arm to the target position. Now we have to fine tune the model so that it mimics the motor control of the brain.

KEYWORDS:

Artificial Intelligence, Neural Network, Motor Control, Neuroscience, Robotics

BIOGRAPHY:

Gautam has completed his Bachelors in Electronics and Communication Engineering from Visveswaraya Technological Univaerity. He is currently associated with Indian Insitute of Science as Research Assistant and also consult companies in building Machine Learning models. He also has started an organization upamanyuAI to open source neuromorphic computing tool